

AUTOMATIC MOVABLE RAILWAY PLATFORM WITH TRAIN ARRIVAL DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

Main aim of this project is to automate railway track pedestrian crossing without use staircase & announce the status of the arrival for platform users. In this system is also used to avoid accident problems. Because, now a day's train accidents are occurring frequently in India. This project identifies the status of each train using IR transceivers and informs it to microcontroller. This project is used to avoid the train collision, thus we save the valuable human lives and losses. So this project is useful for railway departments.

KEYWORDS—Automatic platform; IOT; Railway; Arduino; H Bridge